

The Effect of Chlorides on the Hydrogenation of Nitrogen containing Model Substances

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The present communication deals with the removal of nitrogen from nitrogen containing model substances by catalytic hydrodenitrogenation in the presence of chlorides.

The Co- Mo- Al_2O_3 - HCl catalytic system was shown to be extremely active with respect to hydrodenitrogenation.

Dichloroethane was shown to be a suitable base material for the production of gaseous hydrochloric acid in a high pressure reactor system made of Hastelloy-C.

Removal of nitrogen from oil fractions by hydrofining appears to be more difficult than the removal of sulphur¹⁻³. During hydrodesulphurization of gas oil fractions only 20-50% of the nitrogen is eliminated.

It has been shown by several investigators that for complete nitrogen removal, higher reaction temperatures, 420-500° and hydrogen pressures up to 200 atmospheres are required⁴⁻⁶.

The aim of the present investigation is to explain this phenomenon and to find on the basis of a well understood reaction mechanism more promising process conditions such as :

1. An improved selective catalytic hydrogenation process that can be carried out simultaneously with hydrodesulphurization.
2. An active and stable catalytic system converting N-Compounds at lower temperatures than has been possible so far, starting from the well known Co/Mo hydrodesulphurization catalyst.

1. American Chemical Society, "Symposium on Nitrogen Compounds in Petroleum", 132nd Meeting ACS, New York, September (1957).
2. J. S. Ball and H. J. Rall, *Proceeding API*, 1962, **42**, III.
3. R. A. Flinn, *et al.*, *Hydrocarbon process and Pet.*, 1963, **42**.
4. H. L. Lochte and E. P. Littmann, *The Petroleum Acids and Bases*, Chemical Publishing Company, New York, 1955.
5. F. P. Richter, *et al.*, *Ind. and Eng. Chem.*, 1952, **44**, 2601.
6. F. D. Rossini and F. J. Mair, *Composition of Petroleum*, Symposium on Petroleum Technology, ACS, New York.

In this work quinoline was used as a model nitrogen compound, because it is representative of large organic molecules having basic properties and that the nitrogen is present in an aromatic system.

EXPERIMENTAL

All hydrogenation experiments were carried out batchwise in a Hastelloy-C high pressure autoclave with quinoline as the nitrogen containing base material model substance. In all cases the same Co-Mo- Al_2O_3 catalyst was used.

The influence of hydrochloric acid on the removal of nitrogen from the base materials was examined in a number of experiments, with and without the addition of hydrogen chloride in the reactor system.

Dichloroethane and quinoline hydrochloride were used as a source for hydrogen chloride.

All the chemicals used were of the analytical reagent grade.

Activated cobalt molybdenum on Al_2O_3 catalyst which is usually used for the hydro-sulphurization of oil fractions^{7,8} was used. It was obtained from the Koninklijke Zwavelzuur Fabrieken (Ketjen) in Amsterdam. It is a high density Ketjen hydrogenation catalyst, consisting of cobalt and molybdenum oxides on an aluminium carrier. The properties of the catalyst are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Hydrogenation of Co-Mo- Al_2O_3 -Catalyst

Chemical Composition

(Moisture Free)

CoO	3.50%
MoO ₃	10.00%
Cl	0.04%
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.07%
Na ₂ O	0.01%
C (graphite)	4.00%
Volatile matter, 1200°F for 1 hr.	1.00%
Physical properties pellet size	3/16 inch
Surface area (N ₂) ₂	143 sq.m/g.
Bulk density	1.02 g/ml
Crushing strength (flat plate method)	43 lbs.

7. C. R. Eberline, R. T. Wilson and L. G. Larson, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1957, 49, 661.

8. H. T. Connally, *Oil and Gas Journal*, 1959, 57, No. 38, 88.

The High-Pressure Reactor : To eliminate the corrosion problem a new autoclave was constructed of Hastelloy-C whose properties are given⁹ in Table 2, with a capacity of 0.5 L, (Fig. 1) and provided with a magnetic stirrer of the same metal. The upper end of the autoclave could be closed by a high pressure Hastelloy-C head, with connections for the feed nozzle and an opening for the thermocouple.

Fig. 1—High Pressure Reactor System.

TABLE 2

General corrosion properties of Hastelloy-C

Non oxidizing or reducing media

Material	Acid solution excluding hydro- chloric e.g. phos- phoric sulphoric	Neutral solution e.g. many non- oxidizing salt solu- tion chlorides sulphates	Alkaline solution	
			Caustic and mild alkalies as NH_4OH	NH_4OH and Amines
Hastelloy-C				
55% Ni				
17m Mo	6	6	5	6
16% Cr				
6% Fe				
4% W				

5 = Good to excellent

6 = Normally excellent.

9. R. H. Perry, C. H. Chilton and D. S. Kirkpatrick, "Perry's Chemical Engineer's Hand-Book", McGraw Hill Book Company (1963).

A high pressure Hastelloy-C tube with a capacity of 60 ml. is connected to the autoclave and from this tube the base material could be introduced with a stream of hydrogen into the autoclave. The pressure was adjusted by means of a manometer. The reactor components were mixed by a magnetic stirrer of Hastelloy-C and above it a high-pressure vessel is connected. This vessel was, prior to an experiment, filled with hydrogen to a pressure of 200 atmospheres by letting a stream of hydrogen pass through the stirrer device to the reaction zone during the experiment, so as to prevent the base material from condensing in the stirrer area.

I. Pretreatment of the Catalyst :

a) *Activation* : In order to activate the catalyst, it was treated at 400° with hydrogen at a pressure of 50 atmospheres for 4 hr. The warming-up time from room temperature to 400° was 2 hr. (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2—Activation of the Catalyst.

b) *Conversion of dichloroethane into hydrogen chloride and ethane* : In the present investigation the acid source to the catalyst was dichloroethane. The formation of HCl was carried out by introducing the Co-Mo-Al₂O₃ in the autoclave with the desired amount of dichloroethane. The temperature was raised to 450° to make the dichloroethane completely converted. The warming-up time was 75 minutes and the reaction time 4 hr. The system was then cooled down to room temperature and the nitrogen containing base material was introduced through tube (11) by replacing the feed by hydrogen of a pressure higher than the pressure in the reactor.

II. Hydrodenitrogenation :

For the experiment without addition of hydrogenchloride, the autoclave was loaded with the activated Co-Mo-Al₂O₃ catalyst and purged with hydrogen to remove air.

Before heating to the desired reaction temperature, the autoclave was pressurized and tested for leaks. The measured quantity of catalyst was added followed by 5 ml. of quinoline diluted with 25 ml. benzene. Another 25 ml. benzene was introduced in the same way to ensure that no quinoline was left behind in the feed container.

The autoclave was heated to the desired reaction temperature, 200–450° and the pressure was adjusted to 80 atmospheres, the required pressure level, by adding hydrogen from the high pressure tube (3). The reaction time was kept at the desired temperature-pressure conditions for 2 hr, then cooled down by means of compressed air to 100°.

The volatile reaction product was collected in cold traps, cooled with alcohol and solid carbon dioxide at -76° . The eliminated ammonia was absorbed in 1 N.HCl solution and the escaping gas was collected above salt water in 50 litre gas bottles and its volume determined by a gasometer.

With the HCl catalyst system, ethylene-dichloride was first added to the catalyst and heated at 450° to dissociate it into hydrogen chloride gas and ethane (See I.b.). The system was then cooled down to room temperature and the nitrogen containing compound was introduced with benzene from a high pressure container (11). The temperature was then raised to the desired temperature for 2 hr. and after termination of the reaction the products were analysed for the nitrogen balance by a Kjeldahl method.

The hydrogen chloride gas formed reacted with the formed ammonia to give ammonium chloride. The hydrogen chloride gas evolving from the reactor was collected in sodium hydroxide traps and titrated.

The whole reactor system was washed carefully with dilute sodium hydroxide, water, toluene, and acetone. The washed solution was separated into an organic and a water layer and analyzed for nitrogen.

Hydrodenitrogenation of Quinoline: A number of hydrogenation experiments were carried out at reaction temperatures varying from 200 to 450° with quinoline with and without the addition of quinoline hydrochloride and dichloroethane. In the case of dichloroethane the atomic ratios of Cl/N used were 1 : 1, 5 : 1, and 10 : 1.

Results are shown in Table 3 and the nitrogen balance has already been discussed in a previous publication¹⁰. The residual nitrogen compounds in the reaction media were analysed and identified by G.L.C. on an F and M 500 Gas chromatogram equipped with a thermal ionization detector. The chromatograms for the mixtures of nitrogen compounds formed with and without dichloroethane and with quinoline hydrochloride are shown in Figs. 3, 4, and 5 and were identified by comparison with reference samples.

Fig. 3

10. M. M. Madkour and J. C. Vlughter, Catalytic Hydrodenitrogenation of Mineral Oils and Nitrogen containing Model Substances, Internal Report, Twente University (1957).

TABLE 3

Hydrodenitrogenation of Quinoline

Exp. No.	Starting materials	at ratio Cl/N	in (grams)					Total Nitrogen found back	Total loss of N in grams	% Re-moved N	% Re-sidual N
			Q	B	DCE	Total	Nitrogen				
A	Q+B	0	5.48	43.76	—	49.24	0.59	0.53	+0.06	47	53
B	Q+B+DCE	1	5.48	43.76	2.10	51.34	0.59	0.61	-0.02	32	68
C	Q+B+DCE	5	5.48	43.76	10.48	59.72	0.59	0.64	-0.05	54	46
D	Q+B+DCE	10	5.48	43.76	20.96	70.20	0.59	0.57	+0.02	78	22

Q = Quinoline
B = Benzene
DCE = Dichloroethane.

Fig. 4

DISCUSSION

In the presence of cobalt molybdate catalyst, the mechanism postulated for the hydrodenitrogenation was suggested to be as follows¹¹ :

1. The first step is the chemisorption of the nitrogen compound on to an "active site". The active principle of the catalyst is pictured to function as an acid. The chemisorption is due to the interaction of the basic function of the nitrogen compound with the acid function of the catalyst. The chemisorbed compound then reacts with adsorbed molecular hydrogen to form intermediate nitrogen compounds.

11. R. A. Damon, Hydrogenolysis of Quinoline constituted synthetic shale—Oil, Ph.D. Thesis in Chemical Engineering, Montana State University, 1959.

2. Further catalytic hydrogenation results in cleavage of the heterocyclic ring to form an alkyl aniline.

3. The chemisorption of the alkylaniline by the acid function of the catalyst results in the formation of an anilinium ion. This ion exerts a strong electron attraction and renders the carbon-nitrogen bond susceptible to the electrophilic attack of hydrogen. This results in the formation of a hydrocarbon and ammonia. This step is a simple hydrocracking reaction.

4. The last step is the desorption of the products from the pores of the catalyst.

A rate expression derived from a theoretical consideration of the mechanism proved to fit to the experimental data when it was used as an empirical equation.

In the light of these mechanisms it is easy to picture reaction mechanisms which would account for the hydrodenitrogenation activity of the supported Co-Mo-Al₂O₃ system. However, since excess HCl is present and this material can combine with the nitrogen bases present, the function of the HCl is required to maintain the active catalyst species. About 80% of the nitrogen was removed using the Co-Mo-Al₂O₃-HCl system compared with about 40% without HCl.

G.L.C. analysis :

For all the hydrodenitrogenation reactions whether with or without the addition of HCl into the system, the following general trends were observed :

1. At 200°, quinoline was rapidly hydrogenated to tetrahydroquinoline.
2. At 300°, other hydrogenated products such as, ortho-propyl aniline, o-toluidine, γ-phenyl propyl amine, isoquinoline and aniline started to appear with an equivalent decrease in tetrahydroquinoline concentration.
3. At 400° most of the hydrogenated products reached their maximum concentration with appearance of some higher boiling nitrogen compounds.

The concentration of propyl benzene started to increase alongside with isoquinoline and 5,6,7,8-tetrahydroquinoline.

4. At 450°, propyl benzene, isoquinoline and 5,6,7,8-tetrahydroquinoline reached a maximum concentration. All the other hydrogenated nitrogen compounds decreased sharply.

These trends are to be expected for the hydrogenation of quinoline at lower temperatures favours the formation of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoline and at higher temperatures the formation of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydroquinoline¹².

The hydrogenation of quinoline can however produce a number of other hydrogenated products as shown in Fig. 6 which accounts for the different hydrogenated product obtained.

However, as can be seen from figures 4 and 5, these higher hydrogenated products are formed at much lower temperatures when hydrogenation occurs in the presence of HCl as a catalyst activator.

The hydrogenation reaction with dichloroethane was found to give a much lower yield of *o*-propyl benzene, 19%, at 400° than without it, 45%, the difference being due to the formation of larger concentrations of tetrahydroquinoline, aniline and toluene. This suggest that not only does the presence of HCl in the system enhance lower temperature hydrogenation but also favours cracking reactions.

FIG. 5 DISTRIBUTION OF HYDROGENATED PRODUCTS WITH DICHLOROETHANE

The addition of quinoline hydrochloride salt also follows the same general pattern but its effect is much less than dichloroethane, (Fig. 5).

Fig. 6—Types and Mechanism of Catalytic-hydro-denitrogenation of Model substances.

The relative distribution of the different nitrogen compounds within the same reaction mixture at a particular reaction temperature was found to follow a certain pattern :

1. Orthopropylaniline was found to be in larger concentrations than γ phenyl propyl amine, not only because the amino group is stabilized by the aromatic ring but also because the latter can decompose either by deamination to propyl benzene and/or by cracking of the alkyl chain to give o-ethyl aniline, o-toluidine and aniline.

2. γ -phenyl propyl amine, toluence and propyl benzene were found to form at higher temperatures accompanied with a corresponding decrease of the primary formed nitrogen compounds.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The Co-Mo-Al₂O₃-HCl catalytic system has proved to be extremely active with respect to hydrodenitrogenation. About 80% of the nitrogen, present in quinoline, could be removed in the form of ammonia under mild reaction conditions (reaction temperature = 375° and total pressure = 80 atm.).

2. Due to the highly acidic character of the catalyst ring opening, cracking and skeleton isomerisation of the hydrocarbon part of the quinoline molecule is more pronounced than the non-acid Co-Mo-Al₂O₃ catalyst.

3. There are indications that nitrogen compounds present in mineral oil fractions (e.g. Balayim Oil) follow the same pattern.

4. The mild conditions, mentioned under 1, suggest the possibility of simultaneous desulphurization and denitrogenation of mineral oil and shale oil fractions.

5. The above mentioned favourable results can only be obtained with a large excess of HCl in relation to nitrogen (5 to 10 times the stoichiometric amount).

6. Dichloroethane has proved to be the most suitable base material for the production of gaseous hydrochloric acid in the reactor.

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12. J. Doelman, Deverwijdering van Zwavel en stikstof mit Mineral olien door Katalytisch dodrogeneren. Thesis, Delft, 1962.